

THE IMPORTANCE AND IMPORTANCE OF MARIA MONTESSOR METHODOLOGY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF LITTLE MOTORCY IN ADOLESCENT CHILDREN

Boboqulova Nazokat Yusufvna ,
Termiz state universities
Social fans faculties
Preschool education methodology
chair teacher
+99893 764 51 11

Annotation This in the article today kunda current the identity of the child to develop focused unconventional method - Maria Montessori system and his essence , principles , methods , self specific aspects . Maria Montessori is Italian first olima woman and those guys doctor and pedagogy was . Of Montessori pedagogy advantages and importance about comprehensively illuminated in which Montessori pedagogy _ using of education purpose intellectual development level increase not __ in society to life adapt The need is to create an environment for science centers to learn , to develop interesting and interesting materials The main task of the teacher is to show how to manage the presented materials consists of be , science centers for the child development zone, area to be need about mulohaza referred to.

The key words : Montessori, traditional pedagogy , development environment , toys materials , play exercises to make , to society adaptation , principles , centers , activism .

Maria Montessori own period eng good from teachers one is _ It is traditional pedagogy methods alternative which was technique functional came out . Initially , training system only 3 years old children for designed . Modern teachers by education get on time see and use possible which was all thing asl in the system there is was . Initially education and education for initially special materials functional was released . Maria Montessori toys materials __ Demand did and the word “ **play** ” is an **exercise to do** " with replaced .

Montessori system was originally designed only to nurture children with developmental delays, and Maria created special conditions that allowed students to develop self-management skills to help them adapt to the outside world. It's the students touch sensitivity to develop help giving games due to instead increased. Montessori pedagogy using of education purpose intellectual development level increase not __ in society to life adapt was. But the results of the system founder also amazed by remain because it happened training in the process mental indicators improved.

Based on the data collected during the observation, Maria combined this with existing pedagogical theories and created a system called Montessori. After announcing the results, this method began to be used in the upbringing of healthy children. The program change easy was because he was a student needs easily adapt.

Maria Montessori method a how much principles based on : Maria development eng important phase 3 to 6 years which was childhood age was. He did that of the mind formation this period happen that is with explained. Also his _ theory according to this age reader creative abilities development and goals achieve on the way obstacles eliminate to reach help giving teachers help need.

The essence of this pedagogical technique is explained in free work and creates the right environment to communicate with students. Maria suggested that science centers create an environment for learning, the development of which will be interesting and have materials that will allow you to learn. The main task of the teacher is to show how to manage the presented materials. The set of topics varies depending on the type of class, in which the training takes place.

The essence of the Montessori technique is revealed by this slogan: "Help me do it myself." D emak, this motto, pedagogical the essence of the technique clearly shows that the child is in an independent and free learning. Your child of life certain period known a to knowledge has to be condition not. Your child itself current at the time to him need which was knowledge achieve. The child is didactic materials

with special training environment placed . Teacher child punish , encourage or teaching right has it's not and only necessity at birth to help appeal does . In this case, the child is his own in turn , itself with engaged in materials selection right has _ Har so a child is unique for children evaluation or comparison possible not . Parents _ between this method of the child discipline he said _ there are also doubts . But this so not . In Montessori classes chaos , disorder or noise because no _ all children for amal to do need which was a series rules available :

- if he is busy, do not interfere with another child ;
- Choosing a place for the class - taking into account the views and interests of others ;
- no need to make noise - it can interfere with others ;
- I finished the lesson , put the materials in order and put them in a clean place attention q i l di ring ;
- if the material if busy , wait and watch or do other things .

If we take a closer look at the essence of the Montessori method, it is important to know the six basic principles of this system.

Montessori technique has the following basic principles:

1. Free movement for class .
2. Children learn Montessori special materials .
3. Children independently select and study materials without the help of a teacher .
4. Children of different ages in the group to be
5. Thoroughly trained teacher .
6. Training is carried out in a specially prepared environment divided into different zones

Montessori environment is a separate world where the environment is filled with a variety of fun things and the child is free to choose what activities to do at the moment. The whole environment is filled with specially designed teaching materials in the Montessori method. An important point in a developing environment is

existence. All privileges, without help of the child itself for darsni to choose for designed. From this in addition to the child itself where, how so and who with engage necessary selects the material more more convenient learn for table and chairs free move right has _

Development environment following zones is divided into :

Practical life zonasi - Children and adults of life environment falls. Daily in life need which was all thing bar : lightning without binding breakfast until _ Classes following to groups divided into : yourself care make (clothes and shoes cleaning and put , eat preparation) environment protection make (flowers) irrigation , cleaning) social skills (ethics) rules , communication rules) By the way , all things toy butafori not __ real not .

Emotional development zonasi - To feel like a child and feel _ learns . This zone is development for very much important because _ surrounding the world to know emotional organs using instead is increased . Child colors , masses , shapes , sizes , sounds , even taste and odors such as concepts learns . That's it highlight you need , everyone a training guide only one parameter dedicated to being , it 's just game on time of the child attention attracts .

Mathematics zonasi- this territory touch zonaga depending on and mathematician of materials most theoretical in terms of not __ certain physical in the form of to the child provided are given . That's right so that the child of mathematics essence understand and his age for very much complex problems hal to do very much easy .

Mathematical Montessori style eng strong from the sides one even __ early development other methods supports .

Speech Zone - The child learns the letter, reads it and fills in the phrases. Training also touches on emotions __ based on and it is faster and deeper materials to master help gives _

Space area - The space zone in the Montessori methodology refers to the study of the surrounding world. That's it geography, biology (zoology) and botany), science (various interesting experiments), history and anatomy enters .

Advantages and disadvantages of Montessori technique analysis available .

There are also many critics of the Montessori technique education system, but there are also more followers and supporters. And this , absolutely because it is natural har a thing huge and successful har always to criticize occurs .

The disadvantages are as follows includes : hyperactive children for incompatibility - to fidgets silence observation and to others not to interfere difficult will be .

Different age groups - many parents of " elders " and " youth . " wrong understand and collision are afraid ” creative of the component The absence of, perhaps , critics thought according to the most important is a shortcoming .

Montessori system advantages the following note reach you can :

- Children and adults without intervention education takes ;
- to independence achieve ;
- This method of man freedom educates ;
- self respect to do and to others respect to do warranty ;
- none how evaluation and sentence whether ;
- of the child self respect not to training game in the form of held ;
- child joy with learns ; different age groups .

In conclusion, it can be said that the Montessori technique has been persecuted for many years in wars and in a difficult political environment around the world. Nevertheless, at the end of the twentieth century, it began to recover its popularity . Today, there are almost no parents who have not heard of this method. Now, even in small provinces and cities, there are schools, preschools, and Montessori centers, and the methods they promote and apply are being studied with great interest.

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